

GASTRONOMY TRENDS AS A STRATEGIC FACTOR IN CUSTOMER SATISFACTION MANAGEMENT

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Abstract

The paper aims to describe specific, significantly heterogeneous trends in Czech and world gastronomy and to identify the differences and influence of selected educational levels in relation to customer experience and satisfaction with specific gastronomy trends. Research based on a positivist approach, quantitative nature of data, descriptive, explanatory, cross-sectional studies using the method of abduction, a questionnaire survey technique with Likert scale. Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests are used to assess the normality of the data. Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn-Bonferroni post-hoc test verifies or falsifies the existence of statistically significant differences between customers' experience and satisfaction with gastronomy trends according to customers' education levels. From the analysis of the nature of the Czech customer's consumption behaviours, a more open attitude towards trends of intelligent opportunism can be observed at a higher level of education, while a customer with a lower level of education tends to lean towards trends of Czech tradition and conservatism. Differentiation of customers according to their educational level leads to functional management of customer satisfaction for specific gastronomy trends in relation to the management of strategic initiatives of the enterprise.

Key words

Gastronomy trends, Customer satisfaction, Customer experience, Customer education, Food & beverage industry, Strategic management

INTRODUCTION

The "Food & Beverage" industry is characterised by a highly saturated competitive environment in the battle for customers. In order to win and maintain long-term customer relationships, it is recommended that companies implement activities and tools that reflect the tools and principles of strategic management. Specifically, the principles of leveraging existing competitive advantages (Ketchen et al., 2007),

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aggregate thinking, the creative approach (Mumford et al., 2012), or the element of intelligent opportunism (Pattinson, 2016) as a challenge for introducing gastronomic trends into the offer as one of the driving factors in managing customer satisfaction. One of these tools is CRM for customer relationship management (Yim et al., 2004; Sin et al., 2005) in the hospitality segment (Lin and Su, 2003; Olsen et al., 2008; Sota et al., 2020), with customer value as a key driver (Mahajan, 2020) as a prerequisite to create conditions for customer satisfaction management. Successful implementation of CRM has positive impacts on gaining and maintaining customer satisfaction (Mithas et al., 2005; Alduwailah, 2018) and loyalty as an essential part of strategic business management (Kaplan and Norton, 2008; Rigby and Bilodeau, 2018). As for negative effects, they can be observed mainly due to significant changes in customers' lifestyles and consumption preferences (Hwang and Lockwood, 2006) as it is increasingly difficult to anticipate needs and preferences in relation to consumption and product satisfaction (Chathoth, Olsen, 2007). For competing firms, to survive in the competition for customers, it is necessary to think about the choice of action steps of a strategic nature (Kaplan and Norton, 2008), because of the possibility not only to gain customer satisfaction, but also to get their loyalty and allegiance (Özgener and İraz, 2006; Wu and Lu, 2012; Gharibpoor et al., 2012). However, at the same time, there is the question of the need for closeness and strong bonding of this relationship, which is a prerequisite for long-term sustainability of customer satisfaction, from which it can be assumed to gain long-term customer loyalty (Jiang and Zhang, 2016; Abdullah et al., 2022). To retain the customer to induce a repeat purchase decision, it is essential to achieve high customer satisfaction and loyalty, which are the key performance indicators of CRM (Kumar and Reinartz, 2012; Matsuoka, 2022).

To increase the relationship between the customer and companies (Laidin et al., 2021), the customer satisfaction management should be built on a long-term strategic perspective (Kaplan and Norton, 2008). The strategic nature of this relationship is based on maximising sustainable customer satisfaction, which is a prerequisite for building customer loyalty. A long-term satisfied and long-term loyal customer fulfils Berry's (1995) premise that 20% of satisfied and loyal customers generate up to 80% of a company's revenue. The goal of strategic CRM is to gain long-term competitive advantage (Castellanos-Verdugo et al., 2009) by optimally delivering value and satisfaction to the customer (Kumar, Reinartz 2012). As mentioned above, it can be concluded that customer satisfaction can be related to strategic management of the business.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Implication of a strategic perspective at the level of customer satisfaction management on gastronomy trends

The strategic direction of the business can be understood as means in synergy with gastronomy trends, and so this is at the level of preserving traditional gastronomy and food as a cultural heritage, tasting local specialities to promote regional gastronomy, or the emergence of new, previously untested gastronomy trends with the goal to achieve a memorable experience (Young et al., 2007; Zarei and Jamali Paghaleh, 2011). The success of a strategy consisting of the implementation of gastronomy trends in enterprises is compromised when the enterprise is not able to react in time not only to threats from the external environment, but especially when there is no space to adapt activities, to openness change and new challenges (Chen and Chen, 2002), new, inventive, and innovative products and services, or new gastronomy trends (Chathoth and Olsen, 2007). Investing in new gastronomy trends can also be considered a significant key competitive advantage at a certain time and place (Olsen et al., 2008; Kumar and Reinartz, 2012), whereby a competitive advantage built in this way provides a prerequisite for gaining and consolidating customer satisfaction, trust and ultimately loyalty.

Zablah et al. (2004) define the following four dimensions that reflect the impact of strategic management on customer satisfaction management, completes Rajeh (2014). When applied to gastronomy trends, they can be defined as follows: capabilities (selecting the right gastronomy trends effectively and efficiently), strategy (choosing a long-term or short-term approach to managing gastronomy trends), philosophy (choosing gastronomy trends that will be adaptable in synergy with the corporate image), and technology (selecting the appropriate information and technological practises for their implementation).

Customer satisfaction is defined by Claver-Cortés et al. (2007), Slotegraaf and Dickson (2004), Wu and Lu (2012) as one of the key strategic variables for performance measurement and as a success factor. Ok and Lim (2021) point out that in the catering industry, products, and services of appropriate quality targeted at relevant markets, can also be considered success factors, that in the form of expressing their needs and expectations will fulfil one of the main objectives of the business, which is to maximise customer satisfaction. Kabir and Hasin (2011) add that the product should be personalised, of proper quality (Suh et al., 2015), the appropriate mode of provision (Snyder et al., 2016) and secure (Linghart, 2021). The focus on sales and product uniqueness as a success factor was also discussed by Gursoy and Swanger (2007). All these product characteristics are also fulfilled by trends in gastronomy, which, together with traditional gastronomy products, are taking the level of gastronomy offerings to a higher level. The introduction of gastronomy trends into the offer of an enterprise can be described as one of

the key competitive advantages, enhancing the added value of the enterprise as stated by Olsen et al. (2008). This added value, within a customer perspective, can ideally be expressed as a way of maximising customer satisfaction or minimising customer dissatisfaction.

Customer satisfaction, customer experience (positive or negative), perceived and expected quality, or emotional reactions to consumption of a product or service, i.e., gastronomy trends, are further discussed by Cochran (2003), Oliver (2009), and Cengiz (2010). Evanschitzky et al. (2011) and Al Kurdi et al. (2020), who aptly state that gaining and maintaining customer satisfaction and loyalty cannot be achieved without the synergy of satisfied and loyal employees. Furthermore, they demonstrated that the higher the employee satisfaction, the higher the customer satisfaction. It is this satisfied customer who creates a high prerequisite for attracting new customers (Castellanos-Verdugo et al., 2009).

Description of selected gastronomy trends

Three levels of gastronomy trends can be observed (Sri Susilo and Soeroso, 2014). As a first perspective, trends can be characterised by a significant impact on the rate of decline in households' consumption expenditure around catering. These are ready-to-eat meals and beverages that are the primary meals that provide basic physiological needs with high nutritional value (De Thomas et al., 2019), consumed outside of the customer's home environment. The Barcelona Field Study Centre (2013) includes functional meals, gourmet specialities that provide health benefits and advantages to the customer (gluten-free, glucose-free meals, etc.) among these types of trends, that is, the direction of gastronomy toward the promotion of good nutritional status, the standard of living of the population (Mauriz et al., 2019), and public health (Mutlu and Dogan, 2021). The health benefit for the customer is a balanced diet, a trend also referred to as rational eating, with optimal daily intake and sufficient nutrients, micronutrients, and macronutrients, so that proper function of body organs would be maintained (Aguilera, 2022).

As a second perspective, we can see the connection of trends with a multicultural environment, where individual trends are offered and targeted to a specific type of customer (their social role, status, identity, image, education, age, gender, etc.). Today's customers are becoming more informed, demanding, and hedonic (Lopez Ojeda et al., 2017). These trends consider the everyday life of the consumer, which is influenced by globalisation or internationalisation tendencies. Gastronomy tourism, the clash of different cultures and the change in the consumption habits of Czech consumers have caused food and beverages from foreign, international or even exotic cuisines to frequently increase in food and beverage consumption. This includes, for example, the consumption of insects, notes Simion et al. (2019).

As a third perspective, in the search for harmony between the chef and the opinions of locals and tourists (Sri Susilo and Soeroso, 2014), where based on their collaboration and on the basis of existing and new experiences, as well as on the creation of friendly encounters and relationships, new, often unplanned, unconventional combinations and creations of food and beverages can be observed, with a departure from traditional recipes (Alvarez-Falcon and Serra Majem, 2019), on the basis of experiential gastronomy. Therefore, the gastronomy experience influences customer satisfaction, leading to customer loyalty, as aptly pointed out by Berbel-Pineda et al. (2019).

The unusual pairing of ingredients and foods, a trend known as Food Pairing, can be thought of as the pairing of flavours and aromas. This pairing presupposes a very high level of expertise (Kandampully, 2012) on the part of the chef, intuitively creating suitable combinations or achieving suitable combinations in a random way, notes Coucquyt et al. (2020). With conventional consumer behaviour, a customer might pair traditional cheese with wine or chocolate with strawberries. For an unusual, even exotic pairing, oysters can be combined with kiwi or balsamic vinegar with ice cream. Unusual food and drink pairings can be complemented with edible flowers, which Shantamma et al. (2021) discuss.

Slow Food, as opposed to the Fast Food trend, focusses primarily on the enjoyment of eating and drinking. Williams et al. (2015) points out the philosophy of this trend, which is to build menus according to well-defined principles, such as the use of artisanal techniques in food preparation, with an emphasis on sustainable farming and the processing of indigenous traditional ingredients. Hayes-Conroy (2010) notes that Slow Food also reflects eating food associated with the perception of flavour and aromas, paying attention to buying local and honest ingredients from local farmers, seeking the pleasure of cooking and the enjoyment of eating, as well as discovering new approaches, practises, and trends in gastronomy. Hall et al. (2003) point to an increased interest in local products and foods.

Jones (2017) described the Raw Food menu as a trend toward eating mostly or entirely raw or unprocessed foods, using plant-based ingredients that have not been pasteurised or refined with pesticides. Offiah et al. (2019) also point to the use of waste parts resulting from processing such as pressing, juicing, extrusion, or mixing, which often has a higher nutritional value than the primary product. This avoids food waste and disposal, as Zborowski and Mikulec (2022) point out.

Today, fermented products are highly sought after and are enjoying a renaissance. Zannou et al. (2022) aptly point out that the preparation and consumption of food from fermented products are based on historical and geographical assumptions. Connections can also be sought with the social, cultural and ethnic background of the population. The importance of fermented products such as Tempeh is described by Romulo and Surya (2021).

The popularity of superfoods is growing, mainly due to their antioxidant effect and their high nutritional value. Superfoods and their significant impact on health are reviewed by Liu et al. (2021). Purple foods such as aubergine, blackberries, blueberries, currants, purple potatoes, cauliflower, or asparagus can be considered superfoods. In the Czech Republic, millet, buckwheat, chickpeas, or spelt can be considered forgotten food types, as well as Funk (2015) points out that specific types of forgotten foods differ according to geographical definitions and cultural and ethnic practises. The trend of new gastronomy from seaweeds (phycogastronomy), called sea vegetables (Mouritsen et al., 2019).

With technological progress, the development of new preparation techniques, the discovery of new flavour combinations, and the increasing consumer preferences for mixed drinks in response to new trends and innovations in mixology, the cocktail scene is also changing. Cocktails focused on gastronomy mixology are dominating, with an ever-growing trend for nonalcoholic drinks such as mocktails. Nonalcoholic mixed drinks are enjoying popularity due to the growing healthy lifestyle of consumers (Advanced Mixology, 2021).

The emergence of new foods and beverages can be traced back to the substitution of traditional local ingredients for new foreign ingredients and the introduction of new technological processes in their preparation, states Régnier (2006). Internationalisation trends in gastronomy, such as the penetration of culinary tourism and the migration flow of raw materials, as well as changes in customers' eating habits, have a major impact on the establishment of new products on the domestic market (Pellešová and Vacha, 2022). A product is not considered new until it is sufficiently assimilated into mainstream, mass-consumed products and until the consumer overcomes his fear of the unfamiliar. In gastronomy, pumpkin butter, pasta made from alternative flours, sweet potato syrup, fizzy drinks containing hops, but also forgotten foods such as chickpeas, spelt, millet, or buckwheat can be considered new products. The trend of tasting new products, coffee tasting is also linked to the growing trend of local coffee roasters, where we observe a departure conventional coffee habit (Bučeková et al., 2022).

Despite considerable internationalisation and globalisation, the constant emergence of new gastronomy trends and fashionable fluctuations in gastronomy, the Czech Republic has always had a very distinctive domestic traditional cuisine. The importance of preserving traditional cuisines is highlighted by Lopez Ojeda (2017). Classic, traditional, and home-made dishes can include beef and chicken broth with homemade pasta, cabbage, peas, and garlic soup. Sauces such as cream, dill, mushroom, and tomato sauces play an indispensable role. Main dishes include fried pork schnitzel, roast pork belly, kettle goulash, liverwurst, or drowned pork. There are also ducat buns, rice pudding, or stuffed fruit buns. Regional specialities such as 'Olomoucké tvarůžky', 'Štramberské uší' or 'Valašské frgále' have their place in the Czech gastronomy scene. Home-made and seasonal

food and drinks and their preparation are based on the acceptance of the principle of locality or hyperlocality, the use of indigenous varieties, and the processing of local and common ingredients. The importance of localism in gastronomy is further discussed by Carvache-Franco et al. (2021). The locality of the ingredients is desired and in the preparation of traditional and regional specialities, thus reviving and preserving the Czech culinary heritage (Pellešová and Vacha, 2022). The local identity aspect (Križan et al., 2022) proves to be a principal factor in building customer satisfaction.

DATA AND METHODS

Research context

The research problem of this study stems from the significant atomisation and differentiation of global and local gastronomy trends and the lack of understanding of the influence of individual educational groups on customer experience and satisfaction with gastronomy trends. The objective of the research is to identify the impact of education on customer experience and satisfaction with selected trends in gastronomy. The purpose of the investigation is to highlight differences in customer experience and satisfaction with gastronomy trends according to the educational status of customers. A secondary purpose is also to draw attention to the importance of customer satisfaction with gastronomy trends as a phenomenon that fundamentally influences the strategic management of companies in the "Food & Beverage" industry. The research question is defined as follows: What impact do the various levels of customer education have on customer experience and satisfaction with selected gastronomy trends?

Research sample

The study assumes the use of primary data obtained by conducting primary research, using the method of enquiry with the questionnaire survey technique. 505 Czech Republic respondents were contacted with a relevant and valid sample set of 400 respondents. The empirical calculation for the sample size is the reliability coefficient for the correctness of the obtained statements at the level of 95.4%; with a maximum allowable error of 5%. The data collection period was spring 2022. We explore: which of the trends in world gastronomy have you tried, and which would you like to try? 2 cardinal statistical features are observed, namely: 1) customer education, i.e., an independent statistical feature measured on a nominal rating scale with 4 categories, namely - primary education, vocational certificate, secondary education, and university education; 2) customer experience and satisfaction with gastronomy trends, i.e., the dependent statistical characteristic measured on an interval rating, ordinal five-point Likert scale with 5 categories (1=very satisfied; 2=satisfied, 3=neutral; 4=dissatisfied; 5=very dissatisfied). The following 22 selected gastronomy trends are discussed, namely parameters such as

Days of Foreign Cuisine, Exotic Dishes, Czech Traditional Cuisine, Regional Cuisine, Beetles on a Plate, Edible Flowers, Menu by Slow Food, Rational Menu, Pairing Food with Wine, Menu by Raw Food, Unknown and Fermented Foods, Fusion Cuisine, Unusual Food Pairing, Forgotten and Superfoods, Game Feast, Slaughterhouse Feast, Mixed Drinks, Homemade Seasonal Dishes, Wine or Beer Tasting, New Types of Drinks, Tea and Coffee Tasting, Tasting of New Products.

Research methods

The choice of the relevant statistical test, the correct choice of which presupposes finding out whether the data are worked to meet the normality assumption. The null hypothesis H_0 is defined: There is an assumption of a normal distribution of the data. And the alternative hypothesis H_1 : There is no assumption of a normal distribution of the data. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test with its variant Lilliefors correction and the Shapiro-Wilk test are used to verify or falsify the hypotheses. The results of all tests for the parameters under study showed that the values of the significance coefficient 'Sig' were less than the significance level ($\alpha < 0.05$). We can conclude that we reject H_0 . This means that with a probability of 95% it is proven that the data do not have a normal distribution, and nonparametric types of tests can be used in further testing. Based on the character of the data, the Kruskal-Wallis test is chosen to verify or falsify the existence of statistically significant differences between customer experience and customer satisfaction with the selected dining trends according to customers' education levels. For the parameters, i.e., gastronomy trends, for which a positive dependence is demonstrated, a Dunn-Bonferroni post hoc test is then performed to approximate the specific dependencies between the independent statistical features, i.e., between specific customer education levels, and to confirm or adjust the original p-value by pairwise comparison of the individual independent variables, i.e., by comparing the individual customer education levels.

RESULTS

Figure 1 reflects the answer to the main research question: How do various levels of customer education influence customer experience and satisfaction with selected dining trends? The following hypotheses are established. H_0 : There is no statistically significant difference between customer experience and satisfaction with selected gastronomy trends by customer education. H_1 : There is a statistically significant difference between customer experience and customer satisfaction with selected gastronomy trends by customer education. For values of the coefficients "Sig." (p-value), less than the significance level ($\alpha < 0.05$), it can be concluded that with a probability of 95%, the dependence between the individual levels of customer education and customer experience and satisfaction with the selected gastronomy trends is demonstrated for the following 4 parameters: Tasting of New Products

(Asymp.Sig.=0,000); Days of Traditional Cuisine (Asymp.Sig=0,000); Tea and Coffee Tasting (Asymp.Sig.=0,001) and Slaughterhouse Feast (Asymp.Sig.=0,006). This suggests a differential influence according to the educational attainment of the customers on their experience and satisfaction with the trends of gastronomy. For the other parameters examined, the p-value is higher than the 0.05 significance level, namely: Beetles on a Plate (Sig.=0,065); Mixed Drinks (Sig.=0,117); Fusion Cuisine (Sig.=0,121); Homemade Seasonal Dishes (Sig.=0,150); Forgotten and Superfoods (Sig.=0,187); Menu by Raw Food (Sig.=0,197); Game Feast (Sig.=0,228); Wine or Beer Tasting (Sig.=0,248); Pairing of food with wine (Sig.=0,270); Czech Traditional Cuisine (Sig.=0,292); Edible Flowers (Sig.=0,295); Menu by Slow Food (Sig.=0,307); Unknown and Fermented Foods (Sig.=0,382); Exotic Dishes (Sig.=0,414); Regional Cuisine (Sig.=0,549); Unusual Food Pairing (Sig.=0,796); New Types of Drinks (Sig.=0,810); Rational Menu (Sig.=0,960). It can be remarked that the higher the level of the p-value, the less statistically significant a given the trend of gastronomy is.

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
4	The distribution of Tasting of New Products is the same across categories of Education.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	,000	Reject the null hypothesis.
1	The distribution of Days of Traditional Cuisine is the same across categories of Education.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	,000	Reject the null hypothesis.
3	The distribution of Tea and Coffee Tasting is the same across categories of Education.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	,001	Reject the null hypothesis.
2	The distribution of Slaughterhouse Feast is the same across categories of Education.	Independent-Samples Kruskal-Wallis Test	,006	Reject the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is ,05.

Fig. 1 Gastronomy trends with statistically significant influence between education levels and customer experience and satisfaction.

Source: own research

Figure 2 reflects the answer to research question 1: What are the differences in specific levels of customer education in terms of customer experience and satisfaction on Days of Traditional Cuisine? H0: Customer experience and satisfaction with the Days of Traditional Cuisine are the same across all levels of customer education. H1: Customer experience and satisfaction with the Days of Traditional Cuisine are not the same at all levels of customer education. At

the significance level ($\alpha < 0.05$), it can be concluded that H_0 is rejected. With a probability of 95%, a statistically significant dependence or very strong evidence of dependence exists between at least two levels of customer education to experience and customer satisfaction with the gastronomy trend "Days of Traditional Cuisine". The relationship in the observed parameters can be observed between secondary education and vocational certificate (Sig.=0.009) and between secondary education and university education (Sig.=0.000). Dunn's post-hoc test confirmed only one statistically significant difference between the two levels of education, namely, secondary education and university education (Adj.Sig.=0.000).

Pairwise Comparisons of Education

Each node shows the sample average rank of Education.

Sample1-Sample2	Test Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Test Statistic	Sig.	Adj.Sig.
primary education-secondary education	-3,739	35,602	-,105	,916	1,000
primary education-vocational certificate	-41,176	37,342	-1,103	,270	1,000
primary education-university education	-48,366	36,053	-1,342	,180	1,000
secondary education-vocational certificate	37,437	14,322	2,614	,009	,054
secondary education-university education	-44,627	10,514	-4,245	,000	,000
vocational certificate-university education	-7,191	15,408	-,467	,641	1,000

Each row tests the null hypothesis that the Sample 1 and Sample 2 distributions are the same. Asymptotic significances (2-sided tests) are displayed. The significance level is ,05. Significance values have been adjusted by the Bonferroni correction for multiple tests.

Fig. 2 Pairwise comparison of selected customer education levels by customer satisfaction and customer experience on Days of Traditional Cuisine.

Source: own research

Figure 3 reflects the answer to Research Question 2: What are the differences in specific levels of customer education in terms of customer experience and satisfaction with the Slaughterhouse Feast? H0: Customer experience and satisfaction with the Slaughterhouse Feast is the same at all levels of customer education. H1: Customer experience and satisfaction with the Slaughterhouse Feast are not the same at all levels of customer education. The dependence in the observed parameters can be observed between the vocational certificate and primary education (Sig.=0.009) and between the vocational certificate and secondary education (Sig.=0.007). After conducting Dunn's posthoc test, there is

Pairwise Comparisons of Education

Each node shows the sample average rank of Education.

Sample1-Sample2	Test Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Test Statistic	Sig.	Adj.Sig.
vocational certificate-university education	-20,377	16,728	-1,218	,223	1,000
vocational certificate-secondary education	-41,979	15,478	-2,712	,007	,040
vocational certificate-primary education	87,895	33,670	2,610	,009	,054
university education-secondary education	21,602	11,592	1,863	,062	,374
university education-primary education	67,518	32,070	2,105	,035	,212
secondary education-primary education	45,917	31,436	1,461	,144	,865

Each row tests the null hypothesis that the Sample 1 and Sample 2 distributions are the same. Asymptotic significances (2-sided tests) are displayed. The significance level is ,05. Significance values have been adjusted by the Bonferroni correction for multiple tests.

Fig. 3 Pairwise comparison of selected customer education levels by customer satisfaction and customer experience with the Slaughterhouse Feast.

Source: own research

only one statistically significant difference between the two levels of education, vocational certificate and secondary education (Adj.Sig.=0.040); H₀ is rejected. It can be observed how Dunn's post hoc correction has adjusted the original value of Sig.=0.007 to the new value of Adj.Sig.=0.040, therefore, minimising the significance of this association.

Figure 4 reflects the answer to Research Question 3: What are the differences in specific levels of customer education in terms of customer experience and satisfaction with Tea and Coffee Tasting? H₀: Customer experience and satisfaction

Pairwise Comparisons of Education

Each node shows the sample average rank of Education.

Sample1-Sample2	Test Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Test Statistic	Sig.	Adj.Sig.
primary education-vocational certificate	-38,346	32,545	-1,178	,239	1,000
primary education-secondary education	-42,573	29,992	-1,419	,156	,935
primary education-university education	-78,582	30,387	-2,586	,010	,058
vocational certificate-secondary education	-4,227	15,615	-,271	,787	1,000
vocational certificate-university education	-40,236	16,362	-2,459	,014	,084
secondary education-university education	-36,009	10,394	-3,464	,001	,003

Each row tests the null hypothesis that the Sample 1 and Sample 2 distributions are the same. Asymptotic significances (2-sided tests) are displayed. The significance level is ,05. Significance values have been adjusted by the Bonferroni correction for multiple tests.

Fig. 4 Pairwise comparisons of selected customer education levels by customer satisfaction and customer experience with Tea and Coffee Tasting.

Source: own research

with the of Tea and Coffee Tasting are the same at all levels of customer education. H1: Customer experience and satisfaction with the of Tea and Coffee Tasting are not the same across all levels of customer education. H0 is rejected. In Dunn's post hoc test, there is only one statistically significant difference between the two levels of education, secondary education, and university education (Adj.Sig.=0.003).

Figure 5 reflects the answer to research question 4: What are the differences in specific levels of customer education in terms of customer experience and satisfaction with the Tasting of New Products? H0: Customer experience and

Pairwise Comparisons of Education

Each node shows the sample average rank of Education.

Sample1-Sample2	Test Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Test Statistic	Sig.	Adj.Sig.
primary education-secondary education	-51,598	26,859	-1,921	,055	,328
primary education-vocational certificate	-56,562	29,098	-1,944	,052	,311
primary education-university education	-101,015	27,564	-3,665	,000	,001
secondary education-vocational certificate	4,964	14,380	,345	,730	1,000
secondary education-university education	-49,417	10,950	-4,513	,000	,000
vocational certificate-university education	-44,453	15,658	-2,839	,005	,027

Each row tests the null hypothesis that the Sample 1 and Sample 2 distributions are the same. Asymptotic significances (2-sided tests) are displayed. The significance level is ,05. Significance values have been adjusted by the Bonferroni correction for multiple tests.

Fig. 5 Pairwise comparison of selected customer education levels by customer satisfaction and customer experience with the Tasting of New Products.

Source: own research

satisfaction with the Tasting of New Products is the same across all levels of customer education. H1: Customer experience and satisfaction with the Tasting of New Products is not the same at all levels of customer education. H0 is rejected. After conducting Dunn's posthoc test, all 3 observed pairwise comparisons remained statistically significant on the order of Adj.Sig=0.027 for vocational certificate and university education; Adj.Sig=0.001 for primary education and university education; Adj.Sig=0.000 for secondary education and university education.

DISCUSSION

The research revealed that there is a statistically significant dependence and relationship between the different levels of customer education and customer attitudes in the form of customer experience and satisfaction with selected gastronomy trends. The dependence between customer education and customer experience and satisfaction was shown for the following 4 parameters; Tasting of New Products (Asymp.Sig.=0.000); Days of Traditional Cuisine (Asymp.Sig=0.000); Tea and Coffee Tasting (Asymp.Sig.=0.001); Slaughterhouse Feast (Asymp. Sig.=0.006). Customers with university education have the most experience with the Tasting of New Products and have the highest satisfaction rates. This is followed by customers with vocational certificate, secondary education, and primary education. This is illustrated by the mean rank values as follows: university education=188.97; vocational certificate=144.51; secondary education=139.55 and primary education=87.95. Similarly, customers with university education also have the most experience in showing the highest satisfaction for the Tea and Coffee Tasting trend (mean rank=180.46) and Days of Traditional Cuisine (mean rank=169.7); than customers with secondary education (mean rank=144.45 and mean rank=124.74).

A notable finding for the Tea and Coffee Tasting and Days of Traditional Cuisine is the lack of satisfaction with this trend among customers with less than secondary education (specifically vocational certificate and primary education) that emerges as statistically significant. In the case of the Tea and Coffee Tasting trend, it can be assumed that customers with a lower level of education are not interested (Meena and Sahu, 2021) in trying this trend because of the increasing technological demands on their preparation, the continuous emergence of new types and names of teas and coffees, the preference for traditional and proven types and procedures of tea and coffee preparation, distrust and fear of new tastes and aromas and often exotic and foreign ingredients for the Czech consumer. Another reason may be that customers with lower levels of education consume coffee and tea strictly for the purpose of energising, rather than for the purpose of enjoying these products and taking pleasure from them with the creation of a long-term relationship. They regard their consumption as an obligatory and

conventional event, repeated in regular cycles throughout the day. With the trend of Days of Traditional Cuisine, one can only surmise the reasons why these same customers have not positively expressed their experience and satisfaction, as the popularity of Czech traditional and classic cuisine in general is strongly associated across all segments of the Czech population. For the gastronomy trend of the Slaughterhouse Feast, customers with secondary education (mean rank=176.19) and vocational certificate (mean rank=134.22) showed the highest experience and satisfaction with this trend. The question arises as to why customers with university or primary education did not express their positive attitudes towards this trend. One of the reasons may be the urbanisation factor, that is, the formation and development of urban lifestyles and the increasing concentration of customers with university education in predominantly urban regions and agglomerations where more than 70% of the population lives. It is a fact that the customs and traditions associated with the Slaughterhouse Feast, historically associated with predominantly rural regions, are among the so-called folk food, which in the past was dominant, especially for groups of people who had no education and were poor. The products produced by Slaughterhouse Feast are characterised by lower quality attributes, which can negatively affect consumer preferences and purchasing decisions of university-educated customers. To some extent, the low association of customers with university education and the Slaughterhouse Feast trend is also based on the hypothesis that university-educated customers do not want to degrade their social status, image, and reputation by consuming this trend, i.e., they are concerned about the loss of an individual's status in the community hierarchy due to the low prestige of this trend and its products.

In the context of the influence of different levels of customer education on customer experience and satisfaction with gastronomy trends, it can be inferred and assumed that customers with university education show significantly higher levels of satisfaction with Days of Traditional Cuisine, Tasting of New Products, and Tea and Coffee Tasting gastronomy trends than customers with lower levels of education (Meena and Sahu, 2021). On the contrary, customers with primary education and vocational certificates are less satisfied, for example, with the Slaughterhouse Feast, suggesting that the lower the level of education, the lower the customer satisfaction. At the same time, however, it can be argued that the less satisfied a customer is, the less loyal they are and the motivation to make a repeat purchase decision is minimised. A fundamental finding can be made, namely the significant influence of the degree of customer education in identifying their experience and satisfaction with gastronomy trends, with the nature and character of a particular gastronomy trend playing a significant role.

Interestingly, the higher the level of education a customer has, the more they express their experience in the form of satisfaction with the Tasting of New Products and Tea and Coffee Tasting. This reflects the relationship between customer

satisfaction and the strategic principle of intelligent opportunism, that is, open to new challenges. The following question arises. Can it be assumed that the lower the customer's education, the less willing he or she is to try new products? Can this customer be considered conservative, compared to a customer whose knowledge and expertise are extensive and can be considered an expressive customer? It can be assumed that the differentiation of customers according to the level of customer education leads to functional management of customer satisfaction following the management of the strategic initiatives and perspectives of the company. Certainly, a change in the educational level of customers predicts significant long-term changes in their consumption behaviour - different expectations, attitudes, preferences, and buying habits (Bloom, 1976).

CONCLUSIONS

Customer satisfaction, as a strategic management tool (Berisha Qehaja et al., 2017; Rigby and Bilodeau, 2018) especially in the "Food & Beverage" industry, is an important prerequisite in achieving competitive advantage, despite the rapidly changing and increasingly difficult to anticipate market threats (Chathoth and Olsen, 2007), arising from the external micro and macro environment. Such a unique competitive advantage and valuable activity (Porter, 1998), for a company operating in the catering sector, can undoubtedly be the introduction of gastronomy trends into the company's offer to maximise differentiation from competitors and to diversify the product portfolio. One of the significant strategic objectives in the field of culinary arts, culinary science, and the ever-expanding gastronomy trends is to identify the educational level of existing and potential customers (Sariođlan et al., 2021). The premise is to consider the definition of a trend as long-term, enduring, usable at a strategic level (Campos and Wolf, 2018).

Identifying the specific educational level of the customer, their educational status helps to establish not only a good relationship with the company itself but also to create a space for building satisfaction and trust with subsequent satisfaction for long-lasting loyalty (Eisingerich and Bell, 2008). The different levels of education of the customer, their knowledge and understanding of food science, food technology, food consumption, and applications, in implication to gastronomy trends, primarily determine experience and satisfaction from the consumption of the trend, in addition, to the assumption of rational consumer behaviour, the determination of the willingness to spend money on the trend, and the influence on the actual choice of a particular trend in defining the demanding qualitative characteristics and quantitative requirements. Higham (2009) considers trends (and not only in gastronomy) as drivers of consumer behaviour, with the rate of change of the trend depending on the rate of change of consumer behaviour. The impact on changing consumer behaviour or the implementation of a customer's buying decision is due to a lack of information (Bloom, 1976; Oumlil

and Williams, 2000) or if the customer does not possess the knowledge and skills important in navigating an increasingly saturated market environment (Ward, 1974), where the “Food & Beverage” industry belongs.

Creating, maintaining, and maximising customer satisfaction significantly determines the retention of existing customers and attraction of new customers, repeat visits to a foodservice establishment (Matsuoka, 2022) and business success not only in the short term, but especially in the long term (Enz, 2009). The hypothesis of the intention to repeat visits associated with satisfaction with food service establishments and trends is supported by Stone et al. (2019). The implementation of purposeful strategic business management (Elbana, 2009; Wright et al., 2013) with the acceptance of success factors such as the provision and sale of personalised, quality products (Kabir and Hasin, 2011) and services at the level of the implementation of gastronomic trends in the offer of the business based on a holistic approach (Phillips and Louvieris, 2005) of product portfolio analysis and, on the other hand, the management of customer satisfaction (Meena and Sahu, 2021), associated with the consumption of these products and services in the form of utility that reflects not only customer satisfaction but also, naturally, customer dissatisfaction.

The results of the research showed the significance of different levels of customer education in relation to customer experience and satisfaction with the mentioned gastronomy trends. Opportunities for further research are very evident. The potential for extending the research can be found, for example, in exploring the influence of the territorial factor (rural areas, towns and suburbs, cities) in relation to customer attitudes characterised by experience and satisfaction with gastronomy trends. The idea of using the endogenous potential of a microregion in the context of the development of local gastronomy as a specific strategic objective based on local traditions is supported by Klamár and Čermáková (2012). However, Bujdosó et al. (2019) pointed out the untapped potential of tourism (including gastronomy tourism) as a cardinal factor of the long-term development strategy. This approach to the evaluation of tourism resources is also considered a strategic tool by Dehoorne et al. (2019). The importance of building food outlets and anchoring them geographically with a close commute distance with a primary focus on, for example, the trend of the lunch menu is highlighted by Mocák et al. (2022). The increasing importance of these food outlets in the future is noted by Stone et al. (2019), also by the influence of gastronomy tourism, but also by the implementation of gastronomy trends. Another challenge is to measure customer attitudes towards gastronomy trends such as Street Food, Front Cooking, Fast Food, Food Truck, Coffee/Food to Go, within food outlets such as restaurants, cafes, pubs, alcohol pump rooms, beer gardens, food corners with mobile gastronomy as a night economy and night tourism phenomenon, highlighted by Pawlusiński (2023).

IMPLICATIONS FOR GASTRONOMY

The theoretical contribution lies in the definition of selected gastronomy trends as a significant tool of the product portfolio of companies in the gastronomy sector, which significantly affects customer satisfaction as one of the attributes in building loyalty and long-term strategic-orientated customer relationships. In practical terms, it is a significant change in the educational level of the customer, which determines the change in his consumer behaviour, which is identified by his attitudes, experience and satisfaction with selected gastronomy trends on the territory of the Czech Republic. A key factor in this change in consumer behaviour is the type and nature of a specific trend in gastronomy. The hypothesis was confirmed that the Czech customer, with a lower level of education, is conservative regarding expressing attitudes to new trends and, on the contrary, as the educational status increases, the Czech customer is following the principle of intelligent opportunism. It can be assumed that differentiation of customers according to the educational level of the customers leads to the functional management of customer satisfaction after customer relationship management and customer loyalty as one of the strategic perspectives of the company.

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